

Electronic Supplementary Information

Sulfonic resins as catalysts for the oxidation of alcohols with H₂O₂/KBr

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Figure S1. Swelling behavior of the different resins used in this work: a) Amberlyst 15; b) Dowex 50W×8; c) Dowex 50W×2; d) Aquivion P98 (acid form); e) Nafion NR50. Top: dry resins. Bottom: swollen resins in CH₂Cl₂/H₂O (9:1 v/v).